

Clinical and Demographic Predictors of Preeclampsia Outcomes Among Hospitalized Pregnant Women in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Preeclampsia is a major contributor to maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality worldwide, particularly in low-resource settings. It is characterized by hypertension and proteinuria after 20 weeks of gestation and is associated with significant complications. Despite advances in obstetric care, identifying predictors of adverse outcomes remains a clinical challenge. This study aimed to assess clinical and demographic predictors of preeclampsia outcomes among hospitalized pregnant women in a tertiary care hospital in Bangladesh. This prospective observational study was conducted at Rangpur Medical College Hospital from January to December 2025, including 150 pregnant women diagnosed with preeclampsia. Data on socio-demographic, obstetric, and clinical characteristics were collected using structured tools. Maternal and perinatal outcomes were recorded. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 25.0, and logistic regression was applied to identify predictors of adverse maternal outcomes. The majority of participants were aged 20–29 years and resided in rural areas. Severe preeclampsia was observed in 62.7% of cases. Caesarean delivery was performed in 61.3% of women. Maternal complications included eclampsia (14.7%) and postpartum hemorrhage (12.0%). Low birth weight was noted in 45.3% of neonates, and 40.0% required NICU admission. Significant predictors of adverse maternal outcomes included age ≥ 30 years (AOR 2.41), severe preeclampsia (AOR 6.72), gestational age < 34 weeks (AOR 4.96), and history of hypertension (AOR 3.60). In conclusion, early identification of high-risk women based on clinical predictors is essential for improving maternal outcomes in preeclampsia.

Keywords: Preeclampsia, maternal outcomes, risk factors, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy.

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INTRODUCTION

Preeclampsia is a multisystem hypertensive disorder of pregnancy characterized by new-onset hypertension and proteinuria after 20 weeks of gestation^[1]. It remains a leading cause of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality worldwide, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs)^[2]. Despite advancements in obstetric care, the burden of preeclampsia continues to rise, contributing significantly to adverse pregnancy outcomes, including preterm birth, fetal growth restriction, and maternal organ dysfunction^[3].

Globally, hypertensive disorders of pregnancy affect approximately 5–10% of pregnancies, with preeclampsia accounting for a substantial proportion^[4]. In LMIC settings, the prevalence is often higher due to limited access to antenatal care and delayed diagnosis^[5]. In Bangladesh, recent studies have reported a notable prevalence of preeclampsia, highlighting its growing public health importance^[6,7]. The condition is associated with both immediate and long-term complications for mothers and infants, underscoring the need for early identification and effective management^[8].

The pathophysiology of preeclampsia is complex and not fully understood. It is widely accepted that abnormal placentation and endothelial dysfunction play central roles in disease development^[9]. This leads to systemic inflammation, vasoconstriction, and multi-organ involvement^[10]. Several risk factors have been identified, including advanced maternal age, primigravidity, obesity, and a history of hypertension^[11–13]. These factors contribute to the heterogeneity of clinical presentations and outcomes observed among affected women. Maternal outcomes of preeclampsia range from mild complications to life-threatening conditions such as eclampsia, HELLP syndrome, and acute renal failure^[14]. Perinatal outcomes are also adversely affected, with increased risks of stillbirth, low birth weight, and neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) admission^[15]. Early-onset preeclampsia, in particular, is associated with more severe complications and poorer neonatal outcomes^[16].

Previous studies have emphasized the importance of identifying predictors of adverse outcomes to improve clinical management and resource allocation^[17,18]. However, there remains a lack of comprehensive data from tertiary care settings in Bangladesh that integrate clinical, demographic,

and outcome variables. Most available studies focus on prevalence and risk factors without adequately addressing outcome prediction [6,7].

Understanding the predictors of adverse maternal outcomes is crucial for optimizing patient care. Early identification of high-risk individuals allows for timely intervention, appropriate monitoring, and improved maternal and neonatal outcomes [19]. In resource-limited settings, such evidence is essential for guiding clinical decision-making and prioritizing healthcare resources effectively.

Therefore, this study aims to assess the clinical and demographic predictors of preeclampsia outcomes among hospitalized pregnant women in a tertiary care hospital in Bangladesh. By examining socio-demographic characteristics, obstetric factors, and clinical parameters, this research seeks to provide evidence-based insights into factors associated with adverse maternal outcomes. The findings are expected to contribute to improved risk stratification and management strategies in similar healthcare settings.

OBJECTIVES

The objective of this study was to assess clinical and demographic predictors of preeclampsia outcomes among hospitalized pregnant women in a tertiary care hospital in Bangladesh.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This prospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at Rangpur Medical College Hospital, Rangpur, Bangladesh, from January to December 2025. The study included 150 hospitalized pregnant women diagnosed with preeclampsia.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Pregnant women diagnosed with preeclampsia
2. Gestational age ≥20 weeks
3. Admission to the study hospital during the study period
4. Willingness to participate

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Pre-existing chronic renal disease
2. Autoimmune disorders
3. Incomplete clinical data

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected prospectively using a structured and pretested data collection form. Upon admission, eligible participants were identified based on clinical diagnosis of preeclampsia following standard criteria. Socio-demographic information, including age, residence, education, socioeconomic status, and occupation, was obtained through direct patient interviews. Obstetric history such as gravidity, gestational age, and prior hypertension was recorded from patient history and hospital records.

Clinical assessment included measurement of blood pressure using a calibrated sphygmomanometer under standardized conditions. Anthropometric measurements such as weight and height were obtained to calculate body mass index (BMI). Urinary protein levels were assessed using dipstick methods and categorized accordingly. Laboratory investigations, where available, were reviewed from patient records to ensure diagnostic accuracy.

Maternal outcomes were monitored throughout hospitalization, including the development of complications such as eclampsia, HELLP syndrome, postpartum hemorrhage, and acute kidney injury. Delivery details, including mode of delivery, were recorded. Neonatal outcomes, including birth weight, survival status, and need for NICU admission, were documented immediately after delivery. Confidentiality was ensured by anonymizing patient identifiers and securely storing collected data. Only authorized personnel had access to the dataset.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables. Logistic regression analysis was performed to identify predictors of adverse maternal outcomes. Adjusted odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals were reported. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULT

Table 1 presents the socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants. Most women were aged 20–29 years (52.0%), followed by ≥30 years (33.3%) and <20 years (14.7%). A majority resided in rural areas (64.0%). Regarding education, 34.7% had secondary education, while 18.7% had no formal education. More than half belonged to a low socioeconomic group (54.7%). The majority were housewives (82.7%), with a smaller proportion employed (17.3%).

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Study Participants (n = 150)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	<20	22	14.7
	20–29	78	52.0
	≥30	50	33.3
Residence	Rural	96	64.0
	Urban	54	36.0
Education Level	No formal education	28	18.7
	Primary	46	30.7
	Secondary	52	34.7
	Higher	24	16.0
Socioeconomic Status	Low	82	54.7
	Middle	50	33.3
	High	18	12.0
Occupation	Housewife	124	82.7
	Employed	26	17.3

Table II shows the obstetric and clinical characteristics of the participants. Primigravida women constituted 58.7% of the sample. Most participants were admitted at ≥ 34 weeks of gestation (72.0%). Severe preeclampsia was observed in 62.7% of cases, compared to 37.3% mild cases. A history of

hypertension was present in 25.3% of women. In terms of BMI, 42.7% were overweight and 22.7% were obese. Proteinuria of +2 was most common (41.3%), followed by $\geq +3$ (32.0%).

Table II: Obstetric and Clinical Characteristics (n = 150)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gravidity	Primigravida	88	58.7
	Multigravida	62	41.3
Gestational Age at Admission	<34 weeks	42	28.0
	≥ 34 weeks	108	72.0
Severity of Preeclampsia	Mild	56	37.3
	Severe	94	62.7
History of Hypertension	Yes	38	25.3
	No	112	74.7
BMI (kg/m ²)	Normal (<25)	52	34.7
	Overweight (25-29.9)	64	42.7
	Obese (≥ 30)	34	22.7
Proteinuria	1	40	26.7
	2	62	41.3
	$\geq +3$	48	32.0

Table III describes maternal and perinatal outcomes. Caesarean section was the predominant mode of delivery (61.3%). Maternal complications were absent in 56.0% of cases. Among complications, eclampsia (14.7%) and

postpartum hemorrhage (12.0%) were most frequent. Live births accounted for 84.0%, while stillbirths were 16.0%. Low birth weight (<2.5 kg) was observed in 45.3% of neonates. NICU admission was required in 40.0% of cases.

Table III: Maternal and Perinatal Outcomes (n = 150)

Outcome	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Mode of Delivery	Vaginal	58	38.7
	Caesarean section	92	61.3
Maternal Complications	None	84	56.0
	Eclampsia	22	14.7
	HELLP syndrome	12	8.0
	Postpartum hemorrhage	18	12.0
	Acute kidney injury	14	9.3
Fetal Outcome	Live birth	126	84.0
	Stillbirth	24	16.0
Birth Weight	<2.5 kg	68	45.3
	≥ 2.5 kg	82	54.7
NICU Admission	Yes	60	40.0
	No	90	60.0

Table IV presents the predictors of adverse maternal outcomes based on multivariable logistic regression analysis. Women aged ≥ 30 years had higher odds of adverse outcomes (AOR 2.41; $p=0.016$). Severe preeclampsia was strongly associated with adverse outcomes (AOR 6.72; $p<0.001$).

Gestational age <34 weeks significantly increased risk (AOR 4.96; $p<0.001$). A history of hypertension was also a significant predictor (AOR 3.60; $p=0.001$). Primigravidity and BMI ≥ 25 kg/m² showed increased odds but were not statistically significant.

Table IV: Predictors of Adverse Maternal Outcomes (Logistic Regression Analysis, n = 150)

Variable	Category	Adverse Outcome n (%)	Adjusted OR (95% CI)	p-value
Age ≥ 30 years	Yes vs No	28 (56.0) vs 32 (32.0)	2.41 (1.18-4.91)	0.016
Primigravida	Yes vs No	40 (45.5) vs 20 (32.3)	1.78 (0.91-3.47)	0.091
Severe Preeclampsia	Yes vs Mild	52 (55.3) vs 8 (14.3)	6.72 (2.85-15.82)	<0.001
BMI ≥ 25 kg/m ²	Yes vs No	44 (44.0) vs 16 (30.8)	1.76 (0.88-3.52)	0.112
Gestational Age <34 weeks	Yes vs No	30 (71.4) vs 30 (27.8)	4.96 (2.21-11.12)	<0.001
History of Hypertension	Yes vs No	24 (63.2) vs 36 (32.1)	3.60 (1.65-7.83)	0.001

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated clinical and demographic predictors of adverse maternal outcomes among women with preeclampsia in a tertiary care hospital setting. The findings highlight the significant role of maternal age, severity of disease, gestational age at admission, and prior hypertension in determining

outcomes. These observations are broadly consistent with existing literature, reinforcing the multifactorial nature of preeclampsia and its complications.

The predominance of women aged 20-29 years, with a substantial proportion aged ≥ 30 years, reflects typical reproductive age distribution in similar settings. However, the

study identified advanced maternal age as a significant predictor of adverse maternal outcomes. This aligns with findings from Umesawa and Kobashi, who reported increased risk of hypertensive disorders and complications among older pregnant women [13]. Similarly, Bartsch et al. demonstrated that maternal age ≥ 35 years is associated with a higher risk of severe preeclampsia and poor outcomes [11]. The increased vulnerability may be attributed to age-related vascular changes and comorbidities.

Primigravidity was common in this cohort, although it did not reach statistical significance as a predictor. Previous studies have consistently identified primigravidity as a major risk factor for preeclampsia due to immunological maladaptation [20,21]. The lack of statistical significance in this study may reflect sample size limitations or interaction with other stronger predictors such as disease severity.

A key finding of this study is the strong association between severe preeclampsia and adverse maternal outcomes. Women with severe disease had significantly higher odds of complications. This is consistent with reports by Lisonkova et al., who demonstrated that severe preeclampsia markedly increases the risk of maternal morbidity, including organ dysfunction and eclampsia [14]. Similarly, Rana et al. emphasized that disease severity is a critical determinant of clinical outcomes due to widespread endothelial dysfunction and systemic involvement [8]. These findings underscore the importance of early detection and aggressive management of severe cases.

Gestational age at admission emerged as another important predictor. Women presenting before 34 weeks of gestation had significantly higher odds of adverse outcomes. Early-onset preeclampsia is widely recognized as a more severe form of the disease, often associated with placental insufficiency and poor maternal-fetal outcomes [22]. Herzog et al. reported that early-onset cases are linked with greater vascular and placental abnormalities, contributing to increased complications [16]. The current findings support the need for close monitoring of women presenting early in pregnancy.

A history of hypertension was also significantly associated with adverse outcomes. This is in agreement with studies by Bilano et al. and Yeasmin et al., which identified chronic hypertension as a strong predictor of preeclampsia severity and complications [7,17]. Pre-existing vascular pathology may predispose these women to exaggerated hypertensive responses during pregnancy, leading to worse outcomes.

Although overweight and obesity were prevalent in this study, BMI did not show a statistically significant association with adverse outcomes. Previous research has established obesity as a risk factor for the development of preeclampsia. However, its role in predicting outcomes after disease onset remains less clear. Stubert et al. suggested that while obesity contributes to disease development, its direct impact on severity and complications may be mediated by other factors such as metabolic dysfunction [12].

The high rate of caesarean delivery observed in this study is consistent with findings from other tertiary care settings, where operative delivery is often preferred to reduce maternal and fetal risks [23]. Khan et al. reported similar trends, attributing the increased caesarean rate to the need for timely intervention in complicated pregnancies [3]. Additionally, the substantial proportion of NICU admissions and low birth weight infants reflects the adverse perinatal impact of preeclampsia. Atamamen et al. highlighted that preeclampsia significantly increases the risk of neonatal morbidity, including prematurity and growth restriction [15].

Maternal complications such as eclampsia, HELLP syndrome, and acute kidney injury observed in this study are well-documented consequences of severe preeclampsia. Studies by Tabassum et al. and Wassie et al. have similarly reported these complications as major contributors to maternal morbidity in LMIC settings [24,25]. The persistence of such complications underscores gaps in early detection and management.

Overall, the findings of this study are consistent with global and regional evidence, reinforcing the importance of key clinical predictors in determining outcomes. The identification of severe preeclampsia, early gestational age, advanced maternal age, and prior hypertension as significant predictors provides valuable insights for clinical practice. These factors can be used to stratify risk, guide monitoring, and inform timely interventions to improve maternal outcomes in resource-limited settings.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that severe preeclampsia, early gestational age at admission, advanced maternal age, and prior hypertension are significant predictors of adverse maternal outcomes. These findings emphasize the importance of early risk identification and targeted clinical management. Strengthening antenatal surveillance and timely intervention strategies may improve maternal and neonatal outcomes in tertiary care settings, particularly in resource-limited environments.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest.

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